

**ETHNOPHARMACOLOGICAL STUDY OF ANTI-ALLERGIC IN THE CENTRAL
CIKARANG REGION, BEKASI, WEST JAVA, INDONESIA**

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ABSTRACT

Allergies are a problem that greatly affects the population, and hence the use of antiallergic medications is fairly widespread. However, these drugs have many adverse effects. The use of medicinal plants could be an option, but they need to be evaluated. This research aims to document and preserve the use of ethnomedicine to treat allergies by people in the Central Cikarang Region, Bekasi, West Java, Indonesia. Fieldwork was carried out from November to December 2025 using direct interviews, questionnaires and discussions. Plant species are identified based on standard taxonomic methods, flower morphological characteristics, and where possible, using samples for comparison, as well as consultation with experts and the literature. The plant types obtained were grouped into families according to the Cronquist classification system. Plant names were checked against the Plant List (www.plantlist.org) and the International Plant Name Index (www.ipni.org). This study reports that 30 plant species are commonly used by people in the Central Cikarang Region to treat allergies. Among the various plant parts used, leaves (50.0%) are most often used in making medicine, followed by rhizome (13.3%), fruit (13.3%), stem, seeds, and flower (6.7% respectively), and rind (3.3%). Meanwhile, the most frequently used preparation method was decoction (76.7%) and infusion (23.3%). The results of this research confirm that people in the Central Cikarang Region still rely heavily on medicinal plants for their health care system, especially for the treatment of allergies with the most frequently used parts of the leaves and their use in decoctions and infusions.

KEYWORDS: Traditional medicine, Ethnomedicinal plants, Central Cikarang Region, Allergic.

INTRODUCTION

Allergies are a problem that greatly affects the population, and thus the use of antiallergic medications is fairly widespread.^[1,2] On the other hand, these drugs have adverse effects on the central and autonomic nervous systems.^[3-5] The H1 first-generation antihistamines, inverse agonists of histamine receptors, are the most popular antiallergic medications and are over-the-counter drugs.^[4] However, due to their poor selectivity, there are many side effects such as drowsiness, sedation, and depression of the central nervous system. Being also antagonists of the muscarinic receptor, they cause mydriasis, dry mouth, constipation,

and urinary retention.^[5] Compared to conventional drugs, herbal plants provide many advantages, including cost-effectiveness, broad cultural acceptance, ease of accessibility, and lower side effects.^[6] Currently, research to obtain new antihistamines drugs derived from natural ingredients continues to be carried out, one of which is through exploration of active compounds from natural ingredients, especially medicinal plants that have traditionally been used by people to treat allergies in various regions in Indonesia.^[7-9] One of the Region in Indonesia that still uses herbal plants as an alternative treatment, especially to treat allergies is Central Cikarang Region. This research aims to obtain detailed information

about the use of herbal plants for alternative therapy for allergies in Central Cikarang Region, Bekasi, West Java, Indonesia using a field survey method.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Area

Central Cikarang is located in Bekasi Regency, West Java, Indonesia, with an area of 54.12 km². This area has an altitude of 20 meters above sea level with an average maximum air temperature of 33°C and a minimum of 24°C. Moreover, it is located between 06°21'13" South Latitude and 107°11'12" East Longitude. This area is a tropical climate area that is mostly inhabited by Sundanese tribes (90%) and other tribes (10%). Vegetation in the study area is in humid conditions with an average rainfall of 350 mm/year.

Data Collection

An extensive field survey was carried out to obtain information about medicinal plants from the Sundanese tribe in the study area. To document existing information about medicinal plants from tribal practitioners, several field visits were conducted from November to December 2025 in the Central Cikarang Region, Bekasi, West Java, Indonesia. During the research, ethnomedicinal information was collected from middle-aged and older tribal practitioners in their local language (Sundanese), through direct interviews, questionnaires, and discussions. Information on local names of plants, plant parts used, preparation methods and administration routes (e.g., infusion, paste, juice and decoction) of all ethnomedicinal plants collected were recorded during the survey period.

Botanical Identification

Plant species are identified based on standard taxonomic methods, flower morphological characteristics, and where possible, using samples for comparison, as well as consultation with experts and the literature.^[10] The plant types obtained were grouped into families according to the Cronquist classification system, except for Pteridophyta and Gymnospermae.^[11] Plant names were checked against the Plant List (www.plantlist.org) and the International Plant Name Index (www.ipni.org).

Ethics Statement

All participants provided verbal consent before the interview and gave consent to publish the information they provided.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This research revealed that there are 30 plant species commonly used by the local Sundanese tribe to treat allergies (Table 1). This shows that the study location is affordable in terms of biodiversity. Among the various plant parts used, leaves (50.0%) are most often used in making medicine, followed by rhizome (13.3%), fruit (13.3%), stem, seeds, and flower (6.7% respectively), and rind (3.3%). The use of leaves is reported to be easier to prepare and easier to extract active substances from them for treatment. At the same time, leaves have less effect on the mother plant.^[12] Meanwhile, the most frequently used preparation method was decoction (76.7%) and infusion (23.3%). These results are in line with previous research which reported that the forms of traditional medicine most widely used by the community were decoctions and infusions.^[10]

Table 1: Ethnomedicinal plants, local name, part used, mode of administration, and dosage uses in Central Cikarang, Bekasi, West Java, Indonesia.

No	Species	Family	Local name	Parts used	Mode of administration	Dosage of use
1	<i>Allium sativum</i> L.	Alliaceae	Bawang Putih	Rhizome	Infusion	10 grams once a day
2	<i>Aloe vera</i> Burm.f.,	Asphodelaceae	Lidah Buaya	Stem	Decoction	50 grams once a day
3	<i>Andrographis paniculata</i> Nees	Acanthaceae	Sambiloto	Leaf	Decoction	90 grams once a day
4	<i>Annona muricata</i> L.	<u>Annonaceae</u>	Sirsak	Leaf	Infusion	100 grams once a day
5	<i>Anredera cordifolia</i> (Ten.) Steenis	Basellaceae	Binahong	Leaf	Decoction	10 grams once a day
6	<i>Averrhoa carambola</i> L.	<u>Oxalidaceae</u>	Belimbing	Leaf	Infusion	50 grams once a day
7	<i>Carica papaya</i> L.	<u>Caricaceae</u>	Pepaya	Leaf	Decoction	20 grams once a day
8	<i>Cinnamomum verum</i> J.Presl	Lauraceae	Kayu Manis	Stem	Decoction	25 grams once a day
9	<i>Citrus aurantifolia</i> (Christm) Swingle	Rutaceae	Jeruk Nipis	Fruit	Decoction	2 grams once a day
10	<i>Clitoria ternatea</i> L.	Fabaceae	Bunga Telang	Flower	Decoction	10 grams once a day
11	<i>Cosmos caudatus</i> Kunth	Asteraceae	Kenikir	Leaf	Decoction	50 grams once a day

12	<i>Curcuma longa</i> L.	<u>Zingiberaceae</u>	Kunyit	Rhizome	Infusion	100 grams once a day
13	<i>Garcinia mangostana</i> L.	Clusiaceae	Manggis	Rind	Infusion	50 grams once a day
14	<i>Hibiscus sabdariffa</i> L.	Malvaceae	Rosela	Flower	Decoction	80 grams once a day
15	<i>Kaempferia galanga</i> L.	Zingiberaceae	Kencur	Rhizome	Infusion	100 grams once a day
16	<i>Mangifera indica</i> L.	Anacardiaceae	Mangga	Leaf	Decoction	50 grams once a day
17	<i>Momordica charantia</i> L.	Cucurbitaceae	Pare	Leaf	Decoction	50 grams once a day
18	<i>Morinda citrifolia</i> L.	Rubiaceae	Mengkudu	Fruit	Infusion	60 grams once a day
19	<i>Moringa oleifera</i> Lamk.	<u>Moringaceae</u>	Kelor	Leaf	Decoction	50 grams once a day
20	<i>Nigella sativa</i> L.	Ranunculaceae	Jinten Hitam	Seed	Decoction	10 grams once a day
21	<i>Orthosiphon aristatus</i> (Blume) Miq.	Lamiaceae	Kumis Kucing	Leaf	Decoction	10 grams once a day
22	<i>Persea americana</i> Mill.	Lauraceae	Alpukat	Seed	Decoction	20 grams once a day
23	<i>Phaleria macrocarpa</i> (Scheff.) Boerl)	Thymelaceae	Mahkota Dewa	Fruit	Decoction	50 grams once a day
24	<i>Phyllanthus niruri</i> L.	Phyllanthaceae	Meniran	Leaf	Decoction	70 grams once a day
25	<i>Piper betle</i> L.	Piperaceae	Sirih	Leaf	Decoction	50 grams once a day
26	<i>Psidium guajava</i> L.	<u>Myrtaceae</u>	Jambu Biji	Leaf	Decoction	10 grams once a day
27	<i>Solanum torvum</i> Sw.	Solanaceae	Tokakak	Fruit	Decoction	10 grams once a day
28	<i>Syzygium polyanthum</i> (Wight) Walpers	<u>Myrtaceae</u>	Salam	Leaf	Decoction	30 grams once a day
29	<i>Vigna sinensis</i> L.	Fabaceae	Kacang Panjang	Leaf	Decoction	50 grams once a day
30	<i>Zingiber officinale</i> Rosc.	Zingiberaceae	Jahe	Rhizome	Decoction	100 grams once a day

CONCLUSIONS

The results of this research confirm that people in the Central Cikarang Region still rely heavily on medicinal plants for their health care system, especially for the treatment of allergies with the most frequently used parts of the leaves and their use in decoctions and infusions.

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